

PROCESSING AND PROPERTY EVALUATION OF MUBI CLAY TOWARDS GLAZED FLOOR TILES PRODUCTION

Nathan .C.

C/O Iliya Kaigama: Department Of Chemistry, Adamawa State University, Mubi, P.M.B 25, Mubi
Adamawa State Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Five different types of clay samples were mixed with various percentages of Silica sand to produced glazed ceramic floor tiles. Manual compression force was used to compress the mixture to produce ceramic tiles. The tiles were dried and heated using an electric furnace at a temperature of 1250^oC. the tiles produced were experimentally tested for their porosity, hardness and impact. The results of the properties of the ceramic tiles produced were found to fulfill or present reasonable values with the imported floor tiles in market. The aim of the present work is to produce ceramic glazed floor tiles and investigate the effects of locally available clay samples and additives on the quality and its properties.

KEYWORDS: Ceramic, glaze, porosity, hardness, impact, furnace.

INTRODUCTION

Tiles are thin slabs used for flooring, paving or making drains. They may be made of clays burnt in kilns (ceramic tiles) and concrete (concrete tiles)

The manufacture of ceramic tiles involves careful preparation of clay and compression moulding or extrusion process to be followed by drying and firing operation and/or finally glazing operation.

A mixture of clay and water has unique plastic properties which can be shape and fired inn the kiln at the sintering temperature, the alkali flux gives rise to a molted glass which partly dissolves the other oxides constituents and binds the together on cooling. Therefore, the tiles are glazed by applying to the surface an appropriate powder mix which forms a glass on firing. Ceramic materials are relatively cheap and easily located across the country.

Characteristic of floor Tiles.

The most noticeable of ceramic floor tiles is that they are hard and brittle at room temperature. Mechanical properties are influenced by their structure. Variation in mechanical behavoiur result from the various combination of covalent, ionic and Vanderwaals bonds that exist within the structure. Ceramic floor tiles are usually non – conducting to Electricity. The electrical resistivity decrease with the introduction of impurities in their structure. The have high melting points than commonly used metals and their thermal conductivity fall between those of metals and polymers. Thermal shock resistance is a function of thermal conductivity and expansion co – efficient. Ceramics with a lower thermal expansion coefficient and higher conductivity usually exhibit better thermal resistance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Five different types of locally available clays namely: Digil clay (A), Vintim clay (B) Lokuwa clay (C) Lamurde clay (D), Works clay (E), were used singly as base clays with others as additive and silica as flux (Table 1). The clay lumps as sourced were crushed to smaller sizes, dried and finally grounded into five clay particles. The physical properties of the five clay samples plus the silica sand were determined as given in table 2. The binder used was sodium silicate (waiter glass). This is used to obtain a stable, quick – casting slip in order to have as specific gravity together with a pourable condition. It also gives a firms cast. Fields per was also added to improve the strength of the tiles. The quantity was 5% per volume of the plastic body. This work was carried out in the department of agric engineering, college of Agriculture Adamawa state.

FIG 1. CASTING STAGES

Table 1: Composition and Location of clay's Sample investigated weight.

Base clays	Location	Varying % main composition	% additives composition
Clay (A)	Digil area of Mubi North Adamawa State.	Silica + Clay A(60%)	20% Clay B 20% Flux (feldspar)
Clay (B)	Vimtim area of Mubi Adamawa State.	Silica + Clay B(65%)	22.5% clay C, 12.5% Flux (feldspar)
Clay (C)	Lokuwa area of Mubi North Adamawa State.	Silica + Clay C(60%)	22.5% clay A, 10 clay D, 15% Flux (feldspar)
Clay (D)	Lamurde area of Mubi North Adamawa State.	Silica + Clay D(65%)	10% clay D, 10% clay a, 15 Flux (feldspar)
Clay (E)	Works area of Mubi North Adamawa State.	Silica + Clay E(60%)	20% clay D, 20% Flux (feldspar)

The composition mixes were based on the clays on the clays compositions mixes for the manufacturing of hard porcelain products.

Table 2: Physical properties of clay

S/N	Physical Properties	Clay A	Clay B	Clay C	Clay D	Clay E	Silica
1	Colour	Reddish brown	Creamy grey	White	White	Creamy white	Creamy
2	Specific gravity	2.31	2.03	2.00	2.01	2.62	.2.73
3	Clay content						
4	% Moisture content As received crushed	2.56	1.28	1.29	19.7	18.5	5.67
5	Grain fineness ratio	86.5	69.87	83.82	9.73	64.92	65.4

TILES PRODUCTION

The collected clays were ground to small pellets and then soaked in a drum of water for four days, on the fifth day the wet clays was sieved. A 500 μ m mesh was used. The purpose of the sieving was to remove sand and other organic materials, such as plant roots and dead matter. After sieving the wet clay was poured in a container and allowed to settle to the bottom of the container. The settlement took two days to achieve. After the two days, the remaining water drained off and the wet clay brought out to an open space to allow for more straining of water at standard temperature of about 23%. This process is known as aeration of the wet clay. The aim of the aeration is to bring the clay to a workable state and enable the composition to loose about 60% moisture to the atmosphere. It also makes the composition more plastic. After the aeration feldspar and water glass 5% each were added to the composed clay body. The water mixed clay mixture was kneaded until the mixed clays become plastic and workable. The clay mixture were rolled into ball shape and tempered to store away in a warm dark place for between 5 to 7 days. The tempered clay's samples were moulded by pressing it in a 20cm x 20cm x 0.5 cm to produce a tile of square dimension. The casting was done in four stages.

Stage 1: The plastic body was well kneaded and poured into the mould box, this material fill the box which was placed on a flat board of dimension of 20cm x 20cm 0.5cm.

Stage 2: A piston was used to ram the body well into the box. The piston is also made of wood with square based.

Table 3: Volume of water absorbed by the tiles

Tile	Initial volume of water (V_1)cm ³	Final volume of water (V_2)cm ³
A	1000	995
B	1000	995
C	1000	995
D	1000	995
E	1000	995
Imported Tiles	1000	995

$$V_1 - V_2 = V$$

Where V_2 = Final volume

V_1 = Initial volume

V = volume of water absorbed by the tiles

Table 4: Comparison of properties between Local and imported floor tiles.

Tiles	Porosity (cm) ³	Hardness (mob)	Impact (Joules)
A	5.0	20.0	138.0
B	2.0	19.0	139.0
C	5.0	20.0	140.0
D	10.0	15.0	110.0
E	5.0	20.0	131.0
Imported tiles	5.0	20.0	140.0

Stage 3: Further ramming of the body was obtained, the expected thickness of the tile is 0.5cm and the 0.10cm extra is to allow for any shrinkage during the drying and firing process.

Stage 4: The box was opened from the sides and the casting left on the board. It was allowed to dry under normal atmosphere conditions for 14 days. This was done to avoid cracking during fist firing.

Porosity Test

A knowledge of the porosity of the tiles is important for it serves as a measure of maturity and also allows the evaluation of the clay body for a specific purpose. The entire specimen (imported tiles and locally produced tiles) were immersed in different containers containing equal volume of water, which was measured to be 1000cm³. The tiles were left for a period of 5 days after which they were brought out simultaneously. The volume of water left was measured and tabulated in Table 3.

Hardness Test

The hardness test was done using a scratch test approach. In the test two control test materials were used. A block of limestone and a block of igneous rock. In the an attempt was made to scratch the surface of both the imported and locally produced tiles with first block of limestone and secondly with a block of igneous rock.

In the first test, the limestone was able to scratch both tiles, in the second test the igneous rock was unable to scratch, all tiles, the hardness of all tiles lies between the number of igneous rock and the number of limestone.

Impact Test

The machine used for the test is the sharply impact testing machine. The test was done first for the local floor tiles and then for the imported floor tile. In conducting the test a notch was made on each test specimen. The specimen was supported so that it was loaded horizontally as a simple beam between two anvils with the notch at mid – span.

The striking edge of the pendulum weight strikes the specimen opposites the notch, the energy expended in rupturing the specimen was found by the formula;

$$W_h - W_h \quad (2)$$

Where W = impact load of swinging the weight from a vertical height, h = strike and rupture of the notched specimen and then the load stops at a vertical height (h)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the composition mixes and location of clay's sample investigated by weight.

The reason for mixing the % additives in table 1 is, at a composition mixes less than the one's in table 1 for the various base clays A to E, before drying cracks were all over the tiles and at a composition mixes greater than the one's in the table, the tiles also cracks. Different and several trials were conducted but non could produce a tile after drying.

The percentages used were able to give stable and hard tiles that the properties were compared reasonable with the imported tiles in market.

Table 2 shows the physical properties such as specific gravity, clay content, etc.

For clay samples and silica sand used for the production of ceramic floor tiles. Composition of properties between local and imported floor tiles were give in table3.

For tiles produced from clay sample A, B, C and E their porosity is the same. The water absorbed by the tiles 5cm^3 each, which is the same with the imported floor tiles. Tiles D gave relatively high water absorption 20cm^3 . This higher amount of water may be as a result of the composition mixes.

The hardness test of the locally produced tiles is the same, or compare reasonable with the imported floor tiles which is 20mob. Tiles produced from sample D gave Low hardness of 15mob.

The impact test conducted for both the locally produced floor tiles and the imported floor tiles is the same 140 Joules, except for slight decreased in sample A, B and E. Tiles produced from sample D gave low impact test which is 110 Joules. Linear expansion and shrinkage test could not be done because the glaze will not allow for accounts result. And since the tiles will be used at temperature above 100°C these test were ignored.

It is obvious that the locally produced floor tiles have almost the same strength and quality with the imported tiles. The slight difference in quality might be as a result of the type of binder used for the local production of the tiles, which might be different from are used for the imported tile.

It can also be seen that only D composition mixes could not be used to compare reasonable with the imported clay tiles.

CONCLUSION.

This research work was carried out to shows that we can actually produced or own local floor tiles using the abundant clay we have in Mubi north local government area of Adamawa state, thereby reducing our importation of foreign of tile; this was confirmed by the result obtained from the test conducted. It can be seen clearly that only tiles D composition mixes cannot be used to compare reasonable with the imported clay tiles.

The cost of executing the project is relatively cheap, although, it could have been cheaper if a local kiln was used and more tiles produced.

REFERENCES:

Gilliot, E.J. (2001): "Clay in engineering Geology" 1st Edition Eslevier

Grimehaw, R.W(2003): "The Chemistry and Physics of clays" Ernest Ben Publishers, London.

Peter, S.M. (1998): "Understanding clay, Recognition and processing" Volunteers in Technical assistance, (VITA), USA.

Prienion, A.R. (200): "Glass ceramics, white wares porcelain enamel", A.S.T. M 15:02

Prienion, A.R. (1988): "Construction A.S.T.M 4:05.

Ryan, W. (1998): "Properties of Ceramics Raw materials" Devices Publishe House Ltd New Hilvik.

Samuel, J.O (1995): "Manufacturing of ceramic tiles using firing techniques" M.Eng Research Project
Department of Mechanical Engineering University of Ilorin, Ilorin – Nigeria.

Singh, S.(1979): Engineering materials". Vikas Publishing House Ltd, New Delhi.

Stafford, C.E (1980): "Modern industrial ceramics" 1st Edition Bobs – Merrill Co Publishers, New
York.

Website (2007): Scielo.br/php, pp1 – 8.

Received for Publication: 25/03/2008

Accepted for Publication: 15/05/2008